

Early stage crop/ land cover type classification by using Sen4CAP

Area based application submission process in Lithuania starts at the middle of April. For example, in 2020 declaration of the agricultural land and other areas started at 20 April and lasted up to 22 June with late applications period from 23 June till 17 July. The number of approved applications during the 2020 declaration period was 124 886 with the declared 2 937 305.35 ha area.

Since 2017 NPA has been in a close collaboration with project the Sentinels for Common Agricultural Policy - Sen4CAP consortium. The project aims at providing to the European and national stakeholders of the CAP validated algorithms, products, workflows and best practices for agriculture monitoring relevant for the management of the CAP. The project idea is to pay particular attention to provide evidence how Sentinel derived information can support the modernization and simplification of the CAP in the post 2020 timeframe. NPA contribute to the success of the project with its experience, as well as provide data on the development of new products and test them.

Firstly, agreement with Sen4CAP team was made for 2020 claim year campaign on a scale, goals and earlier than application submission delivery dates. Main idea is to check if any results generated before and during applications submission period could be used as preliminary data. By using results of land cover classification, crop classification and activity monitoring it would lead to availability to check if it provides benefit in the beginning and during declaration period as preliminary data of crop type (summer, winter, land cover, land use). In Lithuania declaration process starts at the middle of April so in order to prepare necessary information before declaration we need to start gathering results from the beginning of April.

For this reason, first task was to check if any results for the 2020 claim year could be generated in April and May – **Early classification phase** by using GSAA validated data from the 2019 claim year (first two rows from the Table 1). Next task was to check if any results could be generated based on the declared parcels at the beginning of the 2020 application submission campaign (third and fourth rows from the Table 1).

Table 1. Used GSAA data and results generated by the Sen4CAP team

Version	GSAA as input data	Sentinel images period	Results
1	2019	01/11/2019 - 10/04/2020	Winter rape, Winter crops, Annual crops, Grassland, Permanent crops, Fallow
2	2019	01/01/2020 - 10/04/2020	Winter rape, Winter crops, Annual crops, Grassland, Permanent crops, Fallow
3	2020 – 10% parcels	01/01/2020 - 12/05/2020	Arable land, Grassland, Permanent Crops, Follow, Winter crops, Winter rape
4	2020 – 50% parcels	01/03/2020 - 28/05/2020	Crop type

Sen4CAP team generated results to check if any results generated before and during applications submission period could be used as preliminary data.

To perform early classifications (with 2019 GSAA as input data) firstly crops are grouped and filtered:

- **Crop code LUT:** the different crop types are gathered together in 6 main classes to classify:
 - Winter rape
 - Winter crops
 - Annual crops
 - Grassland
 - Permanent crops
 - Fallow
- **Parcels filtering:** the by-default filtering options from the Sen4CAP system are applied, and amongst them, only the parcels which are covered by minimum 3 S2 pixels and 1 S1 pixels are classified (for all versions).

Table 2. San4CAP results from 2019 to 2020 years

Predicted crop group	Parcels count					
	2020 S1S2	2020 only S2	2020 only S1	2019_2020 S1S2	2019_2020 only S2	2019_2020 only S1
No prediction	363 483	251 139	363 483	306 650	250 635	306 645
Winter rape	29 703	28 731	29 600	32 667	29 495	31 857
Winter crops	192 212	209 302	179 363	191 343	208 906	183 564
Annual crops	202 219	229 198	191 286	210 458	228 906	199 602
Grassland	383 834	454 277	408 706	430 143	454 241	450 424
Permanent crops	3 063	2 141	2 235	2 987	2 354	2 327

Fallow	4 385	4 111	4 226	4 651	4 362	4 480
Total	1 178 899	1 178 899	1 178 899	1 178 899	1 178 899	1 178 899

From table 2 data, in the period from 2019 to 2020 parcel count remains constant – 1 178 899. No predictions for most fields are set for 2020 S1S2, and for this period a lower prediction was set accordingly for predicted groups. The most accurate and maximum parcels set to 2020 only S2 of which more detectable grassland. 2019_2020 only S2 also detected at least without prediction, but mostly with prediction of which characterized by grassland. According to the declared area, the largest part is winter crops in all predicted crop groups.

To validate and get best results tests with different parameters are performed:

- **6 tests** were conducted:
 - For the period from 01/01/2020 until 10/04/2020
 - With S1 and S2 markers
 - With S1 markers only
 - With S2 markers only
 - For the period from 01/11/2019 until 10/04/2020
 - With S1 and S2 markers
 - With S1 markers only
 - With S2 markers only

Table 3. Validation results

Classes	Metrics	2020 S1S2	2020 only S2	2020 only S1	2019_2020 S1S2	2019_2020 only S2	2019_2020 only S1
Winter crops	F-score	0.88	0.86	0.75	0.90	0.86	0.82
Grassland	F-score	0.90	0.90	0.85	0.91	0.90	0.87
Annual crop	F-score	0.83	0.83	0.75	0.84	0.83	0.76
Winter rape	F-score	0.87	0.79	0.82	0.92	0.81	0.89
Fallow	F-score	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Permanent crops	F-score	0.18	0.04	0.06	0.16	0.06	0.06
Overall accuracy	Overall accuracy	0.8589	0.8499	0.7855	0.8717	0.8535	0.8185
Kappa	Kappa	0.7902	0.7730	0.6770	0.8061	0.7784	0.7226
# classified parcels	/	815416	927760	815416	872254	927760	872254

For both periods, there was a problem in the S1 markers extraction in some specific areas of the country (unexpected). Due to that, the number of parcels that are classified is different between the S1S2 and S1 only classifications, and the S2 only classifications. Still, the number of classified parcels is comparable between the different classifications, which enables to use the validation results. The validation results are based only on the classified parcels, which are the parcels that are located in the areas with no problem.

The OA is higher in the classifications with S1 and S2 markers, compared to the ones with S1 or S2 markers only. The OA is higher with the addition of 2019 satellite data: 0.8717 instead of 0.8589 for the S1S2 classifications. The F-score increases with addition of 2019 satellite data especially for the winter rape crop. But it surprisingly decreases for the permanent crop.

Table 4. Early classification results as preliminary data for the applications in 2020 claim year

	2020 declared	2020 S1S2	2020 only S2	2020 only S1	2019_2020 S1S2	2019_2020 only S2	2019_2020 only S1
Parcels	1 145 511	815 416	927 760	815 416	872 254	927 760	872 254
Area, ha	2 906 642	2 577 892	2 860 065	2 577 892	2 712 191	2 860 065	2 712 191
Farmers	123 145	108 994	122 974	108 994	116 727	122 974	116 727

Figure 1. Early classification results as preliminary data for the applications in 2020 claim year

Best results in 6 crop classes during Early stage classification are generated by using Sen4CAP Crop type algorithm for the 2019 GSAA parcels and Sentinel S2 images. It would benefit 122974 holdings with 927760 parcels and 2860065 ha declared area.

Third iteration results are based on the very first declared parcels at the beginning of the 2020 application submission campaign. Results are generated by using 10% of 2020 GSAA parcels and Sentinels data for the period 2020-01-01 to 2020-05-12. Classification results generated in 6 classes:

- 2 = Permanent crops
- 3 = Grassland
- 4 = Fallow
- 11 = Arable land
- 12 = Winter crops
- 13 = Winter rape

Table 5. Sen4CAP Crop type algorithm third iteration results. 96332 parcels from 15690 holdings.

Group	Parcel count	Area, ha
Arable land	20874	45175,83
Fallow	1214	2488,46
Grassland	53135	80471,35
Permanent crops	1302	1440,22
Winter crops	17120	65428,64
Winter rape	2687	19048,19
Total	96332	214052,7

After comparison of third iteration Sen4CAP results with 2020 OTCS results it was detected that there are 23 cases then preliminary Sen4CAP data would prevent farmer from incorrect crop type declaration (Table 6). Mostly farmers mix arable land crops while on the field it is a grassland.

By using early crop detection results **at the beginning of declaration Pas could enable preliminary checks and prevention of:**

1. Permanent grasslands code mixed with arable land crop codes;
2. Winter crops mixed with other crops;
3. Winter rape mixed with other crops;

Table 6. Examples when early crop type detection would helped farmers after analysing 2020 OTCS results.

Case number	Declared crop type	OTSC crop type	OTSC crop group	Sen4CAP prediction	CT_conf_1
1.	KVŽ	RAŽ	Winter rape	Winter rape	0,7
2.	KVV	KVŽ	Winter crops	Winter crops	0,85
3.	RAŽ	KVŽ	Winter crops	Winter crops	0,785
4.	MIV	KVŽ	Winter crops	Winter crops	0,415
5.	GPŽ	KVŽ	Winter crops	Winter crops	0,964
6.	MIV	MIŽ	Winter crops	Winter crops	0,81
7.	PDJ	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,803
8.	PDŽ	DGP	Grassland	Grassland	0,52
9.	NMI	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,61
10.	PDŽ	DGP	Grassland	Grassland	0,46
11.	AVU	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,567
12.	DOB	DGP	Grassland	Grassland	0,963
13.	DAK	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,399
14.	PDJ	DGP	Grassland	Grassland	0,988
15.	PDJ	DGP	Grassland	Grassland	0,812
16.	PDJ	DGP	Grassland	Grassland	0,664
17.	DOB	DGP	Grassland	Grassland	0,433
18.	AVI	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,461
19.	JSU	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,495
20.	BUL	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,617
21.	MIV	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,589
22.	DOB	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,616
23.	KTŽ	GPŽ	Grassland	Grassland	0,354

Fourth iteration of the crop type map was generated for the period 2020-03-01 to 2020-05-28 by detecting crop type. By using 50% of 2020 GSAA data 40 different crop types were detected and provided in the result file (Table 7).

Table 7. Fourth iteration 2020-03-01 - 2020-05-28 detected crop types

Sen4CAP crop	Parcels count	Area, ha
Winter cereal	95324	368125,18
Grass	233416	367716,05
Spring cereal	64788	162682,91
Winter rape	15951	109768,12
Peas	7760	24273,07

Sen4CAP crop	Parcels count	Area, ha
Beans	2748	19796,07
Black fallow	9866	18477,43
Corn	2155	12408,78
Clover	4159	12010,77
Buckwheat	3271	8558,96
Permanent crops	7776	7156,16
Herbaceous protein plant mixtures	1906	6767,39
Protein crops	3177	6191,8
Agricultural mix	4132	5865,29
Sugar beet	447	5655,25
Lucerne	1320	4128,42
Potatoes	11272	4107,47
Spring rape	512	2575,78
Other crops on arable land	14153	2207,55
Lupin	426	1338,9
Cumin	170	1314,97
Green fallow	634	1236,82
White mustard	683	1214,66
Oilseed radish	156	572,53
Beetroots	155	567,6
Hemp	103	441,84
Bluebell	546	407,21
Nitrogen accumulated plant mixtures	109	350,31
Honey	296	291,65
Other vegetables	1861	262,57
Pumpkins	199	231,5
Onions	102	224,22
Carrots	89	194,49
Radishes	84	184,74
Black mustard	63	168,12
Wikis	41	121,04
Cabbage	95	114,63
Sainfoin	109	99,8
Flax	46	99,05
Garlic	157	59,39
Total	490257	1157968

Fourth iteration results are more like a transition from early detection to a classical area monitoring approach with continues monitoring of eligibility criteria.

After 4 iterations results were summarized (table 8) to calculate parcels count, covered area and farmers count in order to identify most effective timeframe to launch early stage crop/ land cover typed classification by using Sen4CAP software.

Table 8. Early classification results on a different time before or at the beginning of a declaration

	2020 declared in total	2019-11-01-2020-04-10	2020-01-01-2020-04-10	2020-01-01-2020-05-12	2020-03-01-2020-05-28
Input data		2019 GSAA	2019 GSAA	2020 10% GSAA	2020 50% GSAA
Parcels	1 145 511	872 254	927 760	96 332	490 257
Area, ha	2 906 642	2 712 191	2 860 065	214 052	1 157 968
Farmers	123145	116 727	122 974	15 690	67 232

Figure 2. Early classification results

Best results during early stage classification by using Sen4CAP Crop type algorithm are generated with the 2019 GSAA parcels. Based on 2020 declared data on 2020 farmers applications it could be used 927 760 (80%) early stage detection parcels and it would benefit 122 974 (99%) farmers with 2 860 065 ha (98%) declared area.